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Impact of rough and coated building material surfaces on reflection coefficients from 5 GHz to 260 GHz

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Summary

When an electromagnetic wave is reflected by a surface, its amplitude is decreased by the Fresnel reflection coefficients depending on the material permittivity, incidence angle and polarization. Previous analysis showed that the permittivity does not depend on the frequency from 2 to 260 GHz implying that the reflection gain is constant from 2 to 260 GHz for a given incidence angle and polarization. But Fresnel coefficients are only valid for homogeneous material with a flat surface which is not always the case for building materials. Materials may be rough such as for the masonry or coated such as for painted surfaces. The goal of this paper is to assess the reflection gain deviation from the Fresnel coefficients when material surfaces are rough or covered by a finishing layer. The investigated frequencies ranged from 5 to 260 GHz.

1. Introduction

Ray tracing are popular deterministic propagation channel models to evaluate the performance of wireless radio interfaces or to predict the coverage area. They use a geographical database or digital map to compute all possible rays i.e., direct, reflected, transmitted, diffracted, scattered paths, between two or more points such as transmitter, receiver, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS), relay, etc. The ray amplitude and geometrical features are given by physical laws according to the interaction type between the electromagnetic (EM) wave and the environment. This paper focuses on reflected paths. The reflection coefficient indicates the reflection gain experienced by a path when reflected by a material surface. The reflection coefficients are theoretically given by the Fresnel equations for a planar smooth surface bounding an uniform material. They depend on the material relative permittivity ϵ_r , the incidence angle and the EM wave polarization. Many deterministic simulations use the relative permittivity proposed by the ITU-R P2040 recommendation [1] where the permittivity is considered as a constant regardless of the frequency. It implies that the reflection loss does not depend on the frequency. The ITU-R P2040 model is mainly defined up to 100 GHz but recent work performed in the Hexa-X project [2][3] shows that the model could be extended up to 300 GHz with homogeneous and flat surface materials such as glass or plexiglass. Nevertheless, some differences were observed for materials with rough or coated surfaces at frequency above 50 GHz. The goal of this paper is to assess the reflection coefficient deviation from a model considering a constant permittivity when material surfaces are rough or covered by a finishing layer. The investigated frequencies ranged from 5 to 260 GHz.

2. Theoretical models

2.1. Specular reflection

When the EM wave propagating through the air encounters an object, a fraction of the wave is reflected at the interface level air/object. The reflection is specular when the incident wave impinges on a smooth and planar surface and is reflected in a single direction defined by the Snell's laws. The paper addresses only the normal incidence illustrated by **Figure 1**. The reflection coefficient r_{Mut}^{Air} is equal to $\frac{1-\sqrt{\epsilon_{mut}}}{1+\sqrt{\epsilon_{mut}}}$ according the Fresnel equations, ϵ_{mut} being the relative permittivity of the material under test (Mut) considered as a dielectric. The reflection transfer function $H_r(f)$ denoted by $H_r^{spe}(f)$ in case of specular reflection is equal to r_{Mut}^{Air} .

Figure 1: Specular reflection at normal incidence

The relative permittivity does not change significantly with the frequency and can be modeled as a constant regardless the frequency. Hence, $H_r^{spe}(f)$ can be considered as frequency-independent for homogeneous and smooth surface materials. The specular reflection gain (SRG) expressed in dB is equal to $20 * \log_{10}(|r_{Mut}^{Air}|^2)$ and is plotted as function of the material relative permittivity on **Figure 2**.

Figure 2: Reflection gain at normal incidence as function of the relative permittivity

Building materials are not always homogeneous with a flat surface and the Fresnel equations may calculate incorrectly $H_r(f)$. This paper addresses two common situations in building materials: materials with a rough surface and material coated by a finishing layer

2.2. Scattering on rough surface

If the surface is rough, then scattering occurs and the incident wave is scattered into many directions in addition to the specular direction as illustrated in **Figure 3**. The wave power reflected in the specular direction is diminished as a portion of the incident wave is reradiated in various scattered directions. Consequently, Fresnel equations may overestimate $H_r(f)$ in the specular direction when the surface is rough.

Figure 3: Illustration of specular reflection and scattering

A simple approach for accounting the scattering in the specular reflected direction is to multiply SRG by a correction factor ρ_s that depends on the roughness and the frequency. The reflection transfer function on rough surfaces is equal to $\rho_s r_{Mut}^{Air}$. The theoretical Rayleigh-Rice (RR) scattering loss $RR-\rho_s$ defined as $\rho_s = e^{-g/2}$ is often cited in literature as a potential correction factor [4][5]. g is the Rayleigh roughness factor and is equal to $\left(\frac{4\pi\sigma_h \cos(\theta)}{\lambda}\right)^2$, λ being the wavelength, θ the incidence angle and σ_h the surface height variation. $g=0$, $g \ll 1$, $g > 1$, $g \gg 1$ indicates respectively a smooth surface, a slightly rough surface, a moderately rough surface, a very rough surface. $RR-\rho_s$ was calculated according to some assumptions such as a moderate rough surface and a gaussian surface height distribution. It may not be applicable to all building materials. For instance, material with relief surface such as patterned glass is smooth but may reflect the EM wave in many other directions than the incidence one. Additionally, $RR-\rho_s$ model the averaged loss reflection loss due to the scattering but do not model the potential selective frequency fading generated by the interference between scattered paths. Section 4 provides reflection measurement on rough surfaces at a normal incidence and analyses the reflection gain variation depending on the reflection point. It complements the state-of-the-art in EM scattering where the main focus was the power angular distribution of the scattered component [6][7][8][9][10][11][12][13].

2.3. Reflection on coated surfaces

The reflection on coated surfaces such as painted surfaces is a special case of the reflection on multi-layer materials as described by **Figure 4**. Path 1R is the specular reflection on the interface Air/Coating. Path 2R is the specular reflection on the interface Coating/Material. The reflection transfer function denoted by $H_r^{Coat}(f)$ includes the gain of path 1R and 2R and is equal to $r_{Coat}^{Air} + t_{Coat}^{Air} r_{Mut}^{Coat} p^2 t_{Air}^{Coat}$. d_{coat} is the coating layer width and is around 100-200 μm . A comparison between measurements and the model is provided in section 5. It illustrates the coating effect at frequencies above 100 GHz. $ppH_r^{Coat}(f)$ is the power profile of $H_r^{Coat}(f)$ and is equal to $20 * \log_{10}(|H_r^{Coat}(f)|^2)$ when expressed in dB.

Figure 4: Illustration of specular reflection and scattering

3. Measurement campaign

The measurement equipment is based on a vector network analyser (VNA) and frequency extenders. The measurement is divided into three sub-bands defined by the frequency limits of the VNA, extenders, or antennas (5-40 GHz, 110-170 GHz, 170-260 GHz). The antenna is a dual-ridge ultra-wideband antenna for frequencies below 40 GHz and a standard horn pyramidal antennas for frequencies above 50 GHz. **Figure 5** illustrates the mechanical part that allows a free space measurement for reflection coefficients. The material under test (MUT) was placed at normal incidence in front of the Tx/Rx antenna.

Figure 5: Measurement system for material reflection loss estimation

The Tx/Rx measurement antenna can move on a vertical plane and therefore can scan the material by performing a $m \times n$ measurement matrix. A 11×11 measurement matrix with points separated by 1 cm was performed. The role of the measurement matrix is to check the impact of the reflection point location on the reflection coefficient. The raw material measurements are denoted by $S_{11}^{Meas}(f, m, n)$ and corresponds to the S11 parameter collected by the VNA. $S_{11}^{Met}(f)$ is a reference measurement by replacing the MUT with a metallic plate considered as a perfect reflector. $H_r^{Mut}(f, m, n)$ represents the MUT intrinsic reflection frequency response and is computed according to (1),

$$H_r^{Mut}(f, m, n) = \frac{TG[S_{11}^{Meas}(f, m, n)]}{TG[S_{11}^{Met}(f)]} \quad (1)$$

$TG[.]$ is the time gating operator. It is a temporal filter applied on the inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT) of S parameters that rejects all undesirable components such as wall reflections or material edge diffractions. The time gating operator is also configured to keep only the reflection on the illuminated material side facing the transmitter and reject the reflection on the opposite side as illustrated by **Figure 6**.

Figure 6: Illustration of the time gating operator on S_{11}^{Meas}

$ppH^{Mut}(f, m, n)$ is defined as the power profile of $H^{Mut}(f, m, n)$ and is equal to $10\text{Log}_{10}(|H^{Mut}(f, m, n)|^2)$ when expressed in dB. $ppH_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ is defined as the average power profiles of $H^{Mut}(f, m, n)$ and is equal to $10\text{Log}_{10}\left(\frac{1}{mn}\sum_{m,n}|H^{Mut}(f, m, n)|^2\right)$ when expressed in dB. $\sigma^{Mut}(f)$ is defined as the standard deviation of $10\text{log}_{10}(|H^{Mut}(f, m, n)|^2)$ at frequency f calculated on the $m \times n$ measurement point matrix. $\sigma^{Mut}(f)$ characterizes the reflection gain variation due to the different reflection point location.

4. Impact on scattering

Mortars with different roughness degrees and patterned glass shown in **Figure 7** were measured to assess the impact of rough surfaces on reflection coefficients. Mortars A, B, C and D are characterized by a low, medium, high and very high roughness, respectively.

Figure 7: Materials with rough surfaces

Figure 8 displays $ppH_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ for different rough mortars and for patterned glass. $ppH_{mean}^{MUT}(f)$ is compared with SRG computed with permittivity values in line with [1][2] for concrete ($\epsilon_{Mortar}=5.3$) and glass ($\epsilon_{Glass}=6.3$). When the frequency increases and/or when the surface roughness increases, $ppH_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ decreases. For frequencies below 40 GHz, $ppH_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ is close to SRG for mortars A, B, C indicating that scattering is negligible. But at frequencies above 100 GHz, $ppH_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ is reduced compared to SRG by around 5 dB for mortar C and 10 dB for mortar D. The measured reflection gain strongly depends on the reflection point location. For instance, $\sigma^{MUT}(f)$ for mortar A is always lower than 1 dB but reaches 5 dB for mortars C and D above 100 GHz as indicated by **Figure 9**. Scattering may erase the specular reflected path at some points as the reflection gain may be lower than -20 dB for frequencies above 100 GHz. Conclusions drawn to rough surfaces such as mortar surfaces can be extended to any smooth but non-flat surface such as patterned glass.

Figure 8: $ppH_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ for materials with rough surfaces

Figure 9: $\sigma^{Mut}(f)$ for materials with rough surfaces

At the time of writing this document, the different mortars and the patterned glass were being scanned by a laser system to get the height standard deviation and compare the RR scattering factor with the measurement. This comparison will be included in an updated version of the document.

5. Impact of coating effect

As a first step, the reflection transfer functions of single thin layers were characterized as illustrated in **Figure 10**. Polystyrene samples were painted or a paper sheet was stuck on a polystyrene sample. The polystyrene permittivity was estimated to be 1.05 [2]. It means that polystyrene has electromagnetic properties similar to the air and is “invisible” regarding the EM wave. This material is very convenient as it can be used as a mechanical support without interfering with the EM wave propagation. A coat of paint or a sheet of paper set on a polystyrene sample is like a single coat of paint or sheet of paper respectively.

Figure 10: Thin paper sheet and coat of paint.

Figure 11: $ppH_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ and $ppH_r^{Coat}(f)$ for thin layers (paint and paper)

Figure 11 displays $ppH_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ for the sheet of paper and two coats of the same paint with two different thicknesses. It compares them with the coating model described in section 2.3. The paper and paint permittivity values are estimated by minimizing the difference between $ppH_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ and $ppH_r^{Coat}(f)$ and are equal to 3.5 and 2.8 respectively. There are a good agreement between the coating model and the measurement showing that the increase of the reflection gain is due to the interference between path 1R and 2R. For frequency below 30 GHz, the sheet of paper and coats of paint seems to be “invisible” as the reflection gain is less than 20 dB. But at frequency above 100 GHz, the reflection gain is higher than the related SRG for paper or paint.

As a second step, the impact of coating layers was analyzed when the coating layer is applied on a material. The reflection transfer function was measured for raw (CB-Raw), laminated (CB-Lami) and painted chipboard (CB-Paint) samples as shown by **Figure 12**. The laminated chipboard is a raw chipboard coated by a thin melamine layer on both sides. The chipboard permittivity is equal to 2.6 in line with [2] The paint set on the chipboard is the same as the paint characterized previously with a permittivity estimated to 3.5. The paint and melamine layer thickness, the melamine permittivity were estimated in order to minimize the difference between $ppH_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ and $ppH_r^{Coat}(f)$. A good fit was obtained with $d_{melamine} = 125 \mu\text{m}$, $d_{paint}=110 \mu\text{m}$, $\epsilon_{melamine}=5.5$. The conclusions drawn on the visual analysis of **Figure 13** are consistent with the previous conclusions. Thin layers behave like a “high-pass amplifier” at frequency above 100 GHz compared to the reference level given by SRG. At frequency below 40 GHz, the coating layers are invisible, $ppH_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ gain does not depend on the coating permittivity

Figure 12: Chipboard samples

Figure 13: $ppH_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ for raw, painted and laminated chipboards

The last measurements focus on BA13 plasterboard (PB) samples with various finishing multi-layers as shown by Figure 14: raw plasterboard (PB-R), plasterboard coated by a smooth paint (PB-SP), plasterboard coated by a paint with an increased orange peel effect (PB-OP), plasterboard coated by a painted relief non-woven wallpaper (PB-WP), plasterboards coated with a painted relief decorative plaster (PB-DP1 and PB-DP2). All of these materials are multi-layer materials with unknown thickness or permittivity. The paint was different from this used in the previous tests. PB-R itself is a multi-layer material as it is composed by a gypsum panel protected on each side by a thin carton layer. Therefore it is impossible to compare the measurement with a model. This paragraph aims to provide experimental observations with realistic plasterboard-based indoor walls when coating and scattering effects may jointly impact the reflection gain.

Figure 14: Realistic finishing layers based on raw BA13 plasterboard

Figure 15: $ppH_{mean}^{Mut}(f)$ for BA13-based materials

Figure 16: $\sigma^{Mut}(f)$ for BA13-based materials

Figure 15 and **Figure 16** shows $ppH_{mean}^{MUT}(f)$ and $\sigma^{Mut}(f)$ for the plasterboard-based samples. As observed for the chipboard, the coating layers on the plasterboard do not impact significantly $ppH_{mean}^{MUT}(f)$ for frequency below 40 GHz. $ppH_{mean}^{MUT}(f)$ is close to SRG computed with a plasterboard permittivity equal to 2.9 according to [2]. For frequency above 100 GHz, it is still observed that the painted layer increases $ppH_{mean}^{MUT}(f)$ when the frequency increases. $\sigma^{Mut}(f)$ for PB-DP1, PB-DP2 and PB-WP increases with the frequency and reaches a maximal value around 5.5 dB. It shows as for the patterned glass that relief smooth surface can generate diffuse scattering, but it does not imply that $ppH_{mean}^{MUT}(f)$ will decrease as observed for mortar or patterned glass. For instance, $ppH_{mean}^{MUT}(f)$ for PB-DP1 is higher by 2 dB compared to the plasterboard SRG . The coating effect may be predominant compared to the scattering effect.

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